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The space we will live in: Eco-camouflage and environment compaction*.

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Summary

Contemporary living space is interconnected not solely with the subject of interior, industrial and household design or applied arts, but also with virtual and information interfaces. The virtualization of space already at the primary level of a design project becomes one of the key elements of the final implementation, since in the conditions of real space deficit and its alienation from the vast majority, its virtual expansion plays a decisive role, as long as the real environment turns into a virtual interface. Urbanization growth leads to the compaction of the live environment, caused by the alienation of living space not only from the Precariat, but also from the remnants of the middle class, as a part of the existing system of socio-economic relations. In the nearest future one should expect the rise of buildings (as well as entire residential complexes) with virtual eco-camouflage, based on advanced screen technologies, which will shape a new visual ecology. Eco-camouflage will perform the functions of “expansion” and harmonization of the environment, bringing forth the phenomenon that can be called pseudo-deurbanization. Eco-camouflage can also be expanded into the design of public space within the framework of all-sufficient urban areas arising to imitate nature. As a mass phenomenon, eco-camouflage will also considerably expand and re-form the template language that is used to describe and construct urban space (Alexander, 1977), possibly creating some completely new communicative patterns. Virtualization of real environment invites redefining of the supremacy of interface design over industrial design

Keywords: alienation, space, habitat, smart technologies, urbanization, eco-camouflage, environmental design.

The high-speed development of communication technologies integrated into almost all areas of life leads inevitably to a state, when object space transforms into a unified functional, ecological, conceptual and symbolical (denoting the social status of its inhabitants or indicating a particular style) interface. The communication channels presently get accessed not only via market or public environment, but also through the means of private space, by the use of “smart home” and “smart city” technologies; communication interface starts to represent a fully functional dimension of life.

Contemporary living space is interconnected not solely with the subject of interior, industrial and household design or applied arts, but also with virtual and information interfaces. The virtualization of space already at the primary level of a design project becomes one of the key elements of the final implementation, since in the conditions of real space deficit and its alienation from the vast majority, its virtual expansion plays a decisive role, as long as the real environment turns into a virtual interface. At this point design acquires an expanded assortment of tools able to transform the actual reality drastically even with the use of minimal physical resources.

According to research conducted by the UN, primarily the Urban Population Index, the crucial point of the urbanization process in the world was reached in 2007, when the

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number of urban residents exceeded the number of rural ones for the first time in the history. In 2014, the number of urban residents totaled 54%, while by 2050, according to forecasts, about 66% of the world's population will live in cities. Post-industrial consumption has not reduced, but rather enhanced the industrial urbanization. In the conditions of population growth and urban sprawl, a disproportion arises that invites both the superfluity of the artificial environment and the inability to harmonize it with the use of the traditional urban methods. The traditional environmental design, in the capacity it was formed in the 20th century (Kondratieva, 2000), can no longer fulfill the purposes and challenges of the new artificial environment ecology, nor is it able to rely on compensatory functions only.

Urbanization growth leads to the compaction of the live environment, caused by the alienation of living space not only from the Precariat (Standing, 2011), but also from the remnants of the middle class, as a part of the existing system of socio-economic relations. Capitalism is a system in which alienation has always held one of the key meanings. The concept of alienation, developed in German classical philosophy, was then revitalized by Karl Marx in the context of estrangement (Entfremdung) of labor that occurs in the system of relations of production (in his early works Marx uses the term "form of communication") of a capitalist society and the development of its means of production. Alienation emerges in the process of division of labor, taking the form of expropriation of the results and working conditions and alienation of social institutions. It should be noted that in times of modern information capitalism, information and communication technologies can also be regarded as means of production.

In the second half of the 20th century the problem of the alienation of the individual as psychoanalytical matter, being applied to the mass consciousness and political and ideological institutions of totalitarian regimes, came to the forefront; A special role in its unravelling was performed by the Frankfurt school. The consumer society of late capitalism relates us to the Marx's formulation of the problem. Alienation can be defined by two actual meanings: "appropriation" and "eviction". Capitalism literally leads to the alienation of the physical space from the majority of people, allowing them to appropriate it as a private property. The poor are squeezed out to urban ghettos, environmentally disadvantaged territories, etc. The real world (personal house, eco-friendly products, medicine, transport, recreation facilities, etc.) becomes an extremely expensive and inaccessible pleasure. The struggle carried on to access the physical space in the future acquires all the typical features of class struggle.

The city constantly undergoes the process of "fencing-in", when large areas of private property become inaccessible to its residents, and ordinary citizens are forced to engage in wars over public spaces. Urban space is expropriated by private owners and corporation resulting in social segregation of cities. The laboring masses consolidate in socially and environmentally unfavorable agglomerates, as it happens presently, for instance, in Russia, in high-rise, high-density buildings that form closed urban systems – "human anthills".

The goal of design, therefore, will consist not only in the optimization and simplification (or, on the contrary, gamification) of living space, but also in creating the illusion of its existence. This problem concerns not only high-rise but also low-rise buildings, as well as the private sector.

In the nearest future one should expect the rise of buildings (as well as entire residential complexes) with virtual eco-camouflage, based on advanced screen technologies, which will shape a new visual ecology. Eco-camouflage will perform the functions of "expansion" and harmonization of the environment, bringing forth the phenomenon that can

be called pseudo-deurbanization. The matter, however, doesn't inform simply of "decorating" the environment with natural images and colors. Eco-camouflage in no way stands for ordinary "wallpapers" covering the unattractive reality, but, instead, for an interactive eco-environment of artificial reality, the latter being the "avatar" of original, natural environment. Within the system combining screen technologies, optical illusions, reflective materials and, finally, realistic 4-D holograms, it is possible to create fundamentally new dimensions with a high level of interactivity, which will then become the subject of design and implementation. However, the first stage introducing eco-camouflage will be marked by a somehow retrospective return of fashion for environmental design.

Eco-camouflage will represent a vital element of the city of future, since in reality an ordinary person will face a decrease in living space, unavailability of natural materials and food, as well as environmentally friendly places suitable for permanent residence. For the construction business eco-camouflage technologies open up a market that may outperform the construction as it is, in terms of capacity and flexibility: for residents, eco-camouflage will perhaps become the only way to improve living conditions that are beyond improvement in the physical world, which fact creates significant business opportunities, arising from the urge for satisfaction of the natural needs in space and quality of life.

Eco-camouflage can also be expanded into the design of public space within the framework of all-sufficient urban areas arising to imitate nature. As a mass phenomenon, eco-camouflage will also considerably expand and re-form the template language that is used to describe and construct urban space (Alexander, 1977), possibly creating some completely new communicative patterns.

The introduction of artificial ecological systems with areas and spaces based on them leads to the phenomenon of compaction of object environment. The lack of real, physical space and the reduction of personal space along with the simultaneous increase in the availability of "smart" technologies leads to a decrease in the range of familiar things and technical devices and their transition to the area of interactive interface, which will become a priority for UX (User Experience) and UI (User Interface) design.

The process of compaction of object world is already taking its place: the calculator as a program has now become integrated into computer and smartphone, photo and video cameras can be combined into a single type of new mobile device, the concept of a "smart home" makes one reconsider the functional value of other household items, etc. The compaction and virtualization of the objective world corresponds directly to the life model of precariat. It is worthy of note that, given the comparative ease of item manufacturing with 3D-printing technology, it reaching the stage of mass availability can cause the opposite effect, i.e. the glut of supply. Thus, virtualization of real environment invites redefining of the supremacy of interface design over industrial design.

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